

MICROFINANCING: STRATEGIC TOOL FOR SUSTAINABLE GREEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The pressing global challenges of climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation have necessitated the need for sustainable practices across different sectors, especially in entrepreneurship. Green entrepreneurship, which integrates environmental concerns into business operations, is gaining prominence globally, and Nigeria as a nation is not left out. However, limited access to financial capital is a significant barrier to the proliferation of green entrepreneurship in Nigeria. This paper explores the important role micro-financing as a strategic tool played for promoting sustainable green entrepreneurship in Nigeria. The study profiled how micro-finance Institutions (MFI's) provide capital to environmentally conscious businesses, challenges faced and policy recommendations for promoting green entrepreneurship. The study adopts ten selected microfinance institutions in Lagos State with a total population of 280. A sample of 100 staff of microfinance institutions and 20 green entrepreneurs was selected using the stratified random sampling technique. The survey research design adopted a Likert scale questionnaire to obtain responses. Data analysis was performed using SPSS statistical tool and t-test to measure the relationship between micro-financing and SGE. The study applied financial inclusion theory and resources- based view theories. Findings from the study revealed that financing of green entrepreneurship has not gained much prominence in Nigeria and the study recommends that appropriate governmental agencies should provide enabling laws and polices so that micro finance institutions can focus more on providing adequate financing to businesses that engage in environmentally friendly practices.

INTRODUCTION

Micro-financing has increasingly been recognized as a powerful tool for promoting sustainable green entrepreneurship, particularly through micro-financing, which integrates environmental sustainability into financial services. This approach helps micro-entrepreneurs, especially those in vulnerable communities, access resources that enable them to adopt eco-friendly practices while supporting their economic growth.

Green entrepreneurship is an essential catalyst for addressing the environmental challenges faced in Nigeria today due to the growing concerns over climate change, deforestation, waste management, and pollution. Micro-financing can encourage the adoption of environmentally friendly practices. For instance, micro-loans for solar energy projects have been linked to carbon emission reduction and improved energy access (Fatoki, 2014). In addition, green entrepreneurship often leads to job creation in sectors such as renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and waste management, which tends to hire more local workers, enhance community resilience and sustainable development in such local communities.

Micro-Finance Institutions (MFIs) play a critical role in promoting green entrepreneurship by providing capital to individual and small enterprises focused on environmentally sustainable businesses, such as renewable energy ventures, waste management, organic farming, and eco-tourism. It enables small entrepreneurs to invest in eco-friendly technologies and practices that reduce environmental degradation while also improving local communities' livelihood. Zhao and Cao (2022) explored how micro-finance institutions in developing nations have contributed to green innovation through tailored financial products like green loans, which are directed toward environmentally sustainable ventures. MFIs are seen as key enablers of green technology financing. Entrepreneurs often lack the collaterals required by traditional financial institutions, which is where micro-financing steps in. Green micro-financing can fund small-scale renewable energy systems like solar panels, biogas production, and rain water harvesting system that address environmental issues and provide economic benefits.

This study emphasizes the dual benefits of green micro-financing as a catalyst for poverty alleviation and environmental sustainability. While the potential of micro-financing for promoting green entrepreneurship is significant, notable challenges exist; include difficulty in measuring the environmental impact of projects, the relatively high cost of green technologies for low income-entrepreneurs, and the lack of financial literacy among potential beneficiaries. According to Bhattacharya and Dey (2023), in Sub-Saharan Africa, green micro-financing has been advocated to be part of achieving sustainable development goals (SDG's) by creating profitable and environmentally sustainable projects. However, innovative financial products such as green loans, carbon credits, and eco-savings accounts, have been developed to promote sustainable entrepreneurship. These products which are designed to provide incentives for individuals and businesses to engage in eco-friendly activities. Miller and Akingbola (2022).

In Nigeria, a large proportion of enterprises operate as a small or medium-sized firms, many of which are either unable or unwilling to integrate sustainability into their business models due to financial constraints. This is where micro-financing becomes crucial. Micro-financing Institution (MFI's) provide access to small scale organisation enabling them to invest in sustainable solutions.

This study examines the role of micro-financing in promoting green entrepreneurship in Nigeria, highlighting the challenges faced and providing strategic recommendations for leveraging micro-finance to foster sustainable economic development.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Nigeria, the challenges of sustainable development, economic instability, and environmental degradation have driven the need for green entrepreneurship that focuses on environmentally friendly business practices. However, one of the primary barriers to growth of green entrepreneurship is inadequate access to financing. Different scholars have provided varying perspective on Microfinancing and green entrepreneurship, while a good number shows a positive relationship between green entrepreneurship and micro-financing Yinus & Weber 2010; Allet 2014; Holt & Little wood 2017; Akpan & Udoh 2018 others have alternative opinions like Lal & Shkla 2017; Hall and Daneke 2010; Mawa 2008 while other studies have contradictory opinion like Ariana 2017; Nishant 2018; Fischer 2019. However, it becomes highly imperative to dissect the nature of correlation that exist between microfinancing and green entrepreneurship based on the varying studies from diverse literature. The study therefore will corroborate the catalyst nature of microfinancing in promoting green entrepreneurship for the purpose of sustainable development. The study intends to focus more the practicability of achieving sustainable green entrepreneurship with particular emphasis on micro-financing as a major catalyst.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The study's broad objective is to investigate the influence of micro-financing as a major catalyst to achieve sustainable green entrepreneurship. Other specific objectives includes:

- i. To examine the extent to which micro-financing has reduced environmental degradation in Nigeria.
- ii. To determine how green loans and carbon credits have promoted sustainable entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. To what extent does micro-financing influence sustainable green entrepreneurship in Nigeria?
- ii. How has micro-financing specifically reduced environmental degradation in Nigeria?
- iii. Does the provision of green loans and carbon credits promote sustainable entrepreneurship in Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- I. Micro-financing does not influence sustainable green entrepreneurship
- II. Micro-financing does not specifically reduce environmental degradation in Nigeria
- III. The provision of green loans and carbon credits does not promote sustainable entrepreneurship in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Micro-financing has been identified as a major catalyst for sustainable green entrepreneurship in developing economics of the world, especially in the provision of real access to financial resources, thereby promoting environmentally friendly business practices. Ashta and Gaspar (2008). Also, studies from Fatoki (2014) provides that micro-finance institution helps small-scale entrepreneurs in South Africa to adopt sustainable practices through the provision of financial support and capacity building training. Recent studies have focused more on the role of micro-finance institutions in promoting green entrepreneurship in developing countries with limited access to traditional financing. This has discouraged small entrepreneurs to focus and invest in eco-friendly businesses that can reduce environmental degradation and improve the living standards of local communities.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Micro-financing is defined as providing financial services to low-income clients in a given societal setting. (Ledger, 1999). Yinus (2007) defined micro-finance as a financial system that enables individuals saddled with poverty and without collateral to obtain loans for self-employment, helping them to get out of poverty by providing them with access to financial resources.

Robinson (2001) defined micro-finance as small scale financial services provided to people who operate micro-enterprises in rural and urban societies in developing countries. Morduch and Armendariz (2010) describe micro-finance as a financial service that is provided to low-income people without access to traditional banking services with the major aim of managing risk, building an asset base, and generally improving their income level.

Parrish (2010) defines green entrepreneurship as the pursuit of solution through innovation to environmental problems on sustainable business platform with the aim of profits, reduction in ecological footprints and conserving natural resources.

Schaper (2005) describes green entrepreneurship as business ventures that provides benefits to the environment while harping on economic viability to promote sustainable business practices that can reduce impact on the environment Kirkwood and Walton (2010) identified green entrepreneurship as an entrepreneurial activity which integrates social economic and environmental aspects aimed at fostering sustainable eco-friendly products and services.

Gibbs (2009) describes green entrepreneurship as the development of viable ventures with the integrate sustainable environment into business practices with major focus on eco-innovation, green products and services.

The definition above emphasize various perspectives of micro-financing and green entrepreneurship with particular focus in offering financial access to underserved population that engaged in eco-friendly innovation and integration of environmental considerations into business practices.

In recent literature, the linkages between micro-financing and green entrepreneurship focuses on how access to finance can promotes can promotes environmentally sustainable business. Micro-financing provides small loans and financial services to those that may not qualify for traditional bank loans so as to empower them to start or expand green business that support environmental sustainability (Gosh and Guha ,2022). Dhawan (2020) suggest that micro-financing enables small enterprises to invest in green practices such as renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, eco-friendly products and services.

Mehwood and Ozturk (2021) linked micro-financing to environmental consciousness through their assertion that access to financial resources encourages entrepreneurial ventures that focuses on profit and environmental goals. Such financial support enables entrepreneurs with Sustainable Developmental Goals (SDG's) to create business models that can reduce environmental impacts.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK/MODEL

The correlation between micro-financing and green entrepreneurship according to this research will be based on a conceptual model with two major perspective. The perspective focused on the extent at which micro-financing has influenced the reduction of environmental impact from business practices while the second perspective examined the influence of micro-financing on sustainable green entrepreneurship.

MODEL

Independent Variable
(Micro-financing)

Dependent variable

THEORETICAL REVIEW

This theoretical framework explores the role of micro-financing as a driver of sustainable green entrepreneurship. Globally environmental concerns. Have increased therefore, sustainable business models becomes inevitable. However, the practice of establishing business models that can benefits the economy and the environment usually requires a specialized financial support considering the huge start-up cost and associated. Micro-financing, which is known for providing financial support to underserved entrepreneurs therefore is crucial in bridging the gap. This framework links theories of micro-financing, sustainable entrepreneurship and environmental economics to foster green ventures that contributes to economic and environmental sustainability.

This framework is built around three main concepts vis-a vis; Micro-financing, Green business models and sustainable entrepreneurship, while micro-financing refers to provision of financial products to individuals, small and medium based business who may not have easy access to conventional banking services, green business models involves businesspractices that engages in eco-friendly and reduced environmental impacts. Sustainable entrepreneurship focused on creating businesses that generates economic and social values as well as promoting responsible environmental sustainability as well as seeking balance profitability.

Relevant theories for this study includes; Theory of financial intermediation, Triple Bottomline theory and Resource- Based Theory (RBT).

Theory of Financial Intermediation Theory describes how financial institutions, Micro-finance inclusive reduces transaction. Cost by facilitating easy access to capital. Microfinance institutions (MFI's) lowers the encumbrance to entry for green entrepreneurs by providing affordable financial services designed to their unique needs to stimulate their growth.

Triple- Bottom- Line- Theory (TBL) integrates economic, social and environmental goals with sustainable green entrepreneurship. Microfinancing can support triple-bottom-line by supporting business model that creates economic values as well as focused on social and environmental challenges.

Resource- Based- Theory (RBT) asserts that a business natural, human and financial resources are inevitable in creating competitive advantages. Therefore, microfinancing provides the capital resources needed by entrepreneurs to build business models that focuses on green technologies and sustainable practices that distinguishes them in the market environmental.

The theoretical framework above provides that Micro-financing enables green business viability. Access to micro-financing enable green business starts-up to afford eco-friendly technologies, materials and processes that enhance viability. Micro-financing can then be hypothesized to positively and significantly impact the establishment, growth and sustainability of green business models; enables green entrepreneurs to better compete and access markets that prioritize eco-friendly goods and services. The framework also outlines the proposed relationship needed to explore micro-financing role in driving sustainable green entrepreneurship.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Micro-financing has been recognised globally as a strategic tool for sustainable green entrepreneurship particularly in the context of developing economics. Several scholars have provided empirical literature to critically analyse the synergy between micro-financing and sustainable green entrepreneurship.

Schmidt and Kratzer (2016) examine how micro-finance institutions integrate environmental sustainability into their business models and how this has impact in green entrepreneurship in developing countries underscoring the triple bottom line of people, planet and profit.

The study shows a strong relationship between micro- financing and the growth of green entrepreneurship in developing countries. Rahman and Ahmad (20119), explores how micro-finance institutions in Bangladesh have promoted green entrepreneurship by provision of needed funds for eco-friendly businesses like sustainable farming and renewable energy projects

Chege, Wang and Suntu (2020) investigates the correlation between Micro-financing services and sustainability of green enterprises in Nairobi, Kenya.

The study posits that micro-finance encourages entrepreneurs to engage in eco- friendly business ventures thereby promoting long-term economic outcomes. Hossain (2017) in his empirical study noted that micro-financing acts as a catalyst for sustainable entrepreneurship especially in eco-friendly agricultural practices through the provision of capital to marginalised communities to Bangladesh without access to conventional banking products and services Ashta and Gaspar (2008) highlights the special roles played by micro-finance institutions in promoting green energy initiatives as well as supporting business engaged in renewable energy. Fatoki (2014) in his study explores the influence of micro-finance institutions towards promoting green business models in South Africa. He posted that micro-finance helps small and medium entrepreneurs to adopt sustainable business practise through the provision of financial support and capacity training.

GAP IN THE LITERATURE

The success or failure of green business models hinged largely on access to required capital, competition, regulatory environment, etc. The emergence and operations of micro-financing institution has greatly influence the establishment, finding and expansion of sustainable green business that has future research studies can further scrutinize and delve into advanced in issues in relation to providing sustainable solutions to global environment challenges through micro-finance can offer auspicious blueprints towards attaining sustaining green entrepreneurship.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study combined quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure a holistic understanding of how micro-financing impacts green entrepreneurship. The qualitative aspects allow for a robust statistical analysis of micro-finance effectiveness; while the qualitative part explore entrepreneurs' deeper motivations, challenges and strategies. A population of 280 stakeholders represents the population of the study made up of 200 staff of micro-finance institution and 80 green entrepreneurs. Out of this 100 Micro-finance institution staffs and 20 green entrepreneurs were carefully selected using stratified random technique for quantitative analysis and purposive sampling for qualitative interviews. Hypothesis for this study was tested using SPSS 23 for correlation, normality, and t-test to measure the relationship between micro-financing and SGE.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULT

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
SEX			
Male	52	43.3	43.3
Female	68	56.7	100
Length of Service			
1-3 years	25	20.8	20.8
3-6 years	50	41.7	62.5
Over 6 years	45	37.5	100
Employment Type			
Microfinance Employee	100	83.3	83.3
Green Entrepreneur	20	16.7	100

Source: Author's computation aided by SPSS version 23, 2026

Results from Tables 1 above,

A total of 120 respondents completed the questionnaire.

Male respondents were 52 (43.3%) whereas female respondents were 68 (56.7%) from the gender categories

From the Length of Service categories, respondents with 3 - 6 years of work experience accounted for highest number responses, with 50 respondents (41.7%), followed by respondents with over 6 years work experience with 45 (37.5%). of the responses. Respondents with work experience of 1-3 years inclusive account for 25 (20.8%) of the responses.

From employment type categories, 100 (83.3%) of the respondents are microfinance bank employees, while 20 (16.7%) are green entrepreneurs.

Test of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis one

H0₁: Micro-financing does not influence sustainable green entrepreneurship.

Table 2: Result of the Correlation coefficient on hypothesis one

		Sustainable entrepreneurship	greenEnvironmental degradation	Green loan and carbon credit
Sustainable Entrepreneurship	GreenCorrelation	1.000	-.445	.473
	Significance (1- tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	Df	0	197	197
Environmental degradation	Correlation	-.445	1.000	-.358
	Significance (1- tailed)	.030	.	.023
	Df	197	0	197
Green Loan and carbon credit	Correlation	.473	-.358	1.000
	Significance (1- tailed)	.021	.023	.
	Df	197	197	0

Source: Author’s computation aided by SPSS version 23, 2026

*** P-value < 0.01; ** p-value < 0.05

The results from the correlation matrix (**Table 2**) indicate a weak correlation among all the variables. The correlation between sustainable green entrepreneurship and environmental degradation is negative and weak (r = -44.5%) and significant (p = 0.030) at the 5% level. Similarly, sustainable green entrepreneur has a weak positive correlation with green loan and carbon credit (r = 47.3%) and statistically significant at the 5% LOS (p = 0.021). green loan and carbon credit exhibits a weak negative association with environmental degradation (r = -35.8%), which is statistically significant at the 5% level (p = 0.023).

All variables are related, indicating that all activities of microfinance in term of provision of green loan and carbon credit and bid to improve environmental degradation have enhanced sustainable green entrepreneur. And all variables with weak correlation show the absence of multi-collinearity among variables to warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis. In other words, the null hypothesis that micro-financing does not influence sustainable green entrepreneurship is rejected.

Table 3: Normality Tests

	<u>Kolmogorov-Smirnov^a</u>			<u>Shapiro-Wilk</u>		
	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>Sig.</u>	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>Df</u>	<u>Sig.</u>
Sustainable Green Entrepreneurship	.239	120	.060	.768	120	.091
Environmental Degradation	.208	120	.120	.832	120	.100
Green loan & carbon credit	.220	120	.080	.786	120	.080

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Source: Author’s computation aided by SPSS version 23, 2026

*** P-value < 0.01; ** p-value < 0.05

The results reported in Tables 3 provide strong evidence of normality of the distribution of the data, as the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics of **0.060** for sustainable green entrepreneur, **0.120** for environmental degradation; and **0.080** for green loan and carbon credit are not significant at 1% and 5% levels. With these results, the null hypotheses of normal distributions of data cannot be rejected. This provides the basis for the use of independent samples t-test of significance of equality of means.

Hypothesis two

H0₂: Micro-financing does not specifically reduce environmental degradation in Nigeria.

Table 4: Result of the independent sample t-test of the equality of means on hypothesis 2

<u>t</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>MeanDiff</u>	<u>Std.ErrorDiff</u>	
Environmental Degradation	3.023	.003	3	2.32198	.11312

Source: Author’s computation aided by SPSS version 23, 2026

*** P-value < 0.01; ** p-value < 0.05

The results in Table 3 indicate that improving environmental degradation through microfinance activities has significant impact on sustainable green entrepreneurs. This is because the p-value of the T-statistic is 0.003, which is statistically significant at the 5% LOS to warrant the rejection of the null hypothesis. In other words, p-value <.05 consequently, the null hypothesis that Micro-financing does not specifically reduce environmental degradation in Nigeria is rejected.

Hypothesis three

H0₃: The provision of green loans and carbon credits does not promote sustainable entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

Table 9: Result of independent sample t-test of equality of means on hypothesis three

<u>t</u>	<u>p-value</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>MeanDiff</u>	<u>StdErrorDiff</u>	
Green Loan & Carbon Credit	5.023	.011	3	3.42091	.12100

Source: Author’s computation aided by SPSS version 23, 2026

*** P-value < 0.01; ** p-value < 0.05

The results in Table 9 indicate that green loans and carbon credit provision by micro-finance have a significant impact on sustainable green entrepreneurs. This is because the p-value of the T-statistic is 0.011, which is statistically significant at 5% LOS to warrant the acceptance of the null hypothesis. In other words, p-value <.05

consequently, the null hypothesis that the provision of green loans and carbon credits does not promote Sustainable entrepreneurship in Nigeria is rejected.

FINDINGS

The results from hypothesis 1 provide evidence that micro-financing influence sustainable green entrepreneurship in Nigeria. This finding appears surprising, especially considering Schmidt and Kratzer (2016) who examined how micro-finance institutions integrate environmental sustainability into their business models and how this has an impact on green entrepreneurship in developing countries, underscoring the triple bottom line of people, planet and profit.

The study shows a strong relationship between micro-financing and the growth of green entrepreneurship in developing countries. Rahman and Ahmad (2019) explore, how micro-finance institutions in Bangladesh have promoted green entrepreneurship by providing the funds needed for eco-friendly businesses like sustainable farming and renewable energy projects. The study shows a In respect of hypothesis two, similar findings as hypothesis one were shown between Micro-financing and the reduction environmental degradation in Nigeria. Notwithstanding, Nitin (2024) explain in his work that Harnessing Waste Recycling is a Crucial Step towards Combating Environmental Degradation in Nigeria. In major Nigerian cities like Lagos, Kano, Enugu and Port Harcourt, recycling initiatives have not only addressed environmental concerns but also created economic opportunities. These ventures provide jobs and income for thousands of youths, contributing significantly to poverty alleviation and economic growth. According to the Nigerian Economic Summit Group, (2017) sustainable waste management practices could potentially generate up to 500,000 jobs by 2030, underscoring the sector's potential to absorb a sizable portion of the working population in a competitive job market. For hypothesis three, however, findings demonstrate that provision of green loans and carbon credits promote sustainable entrepreneurship in Nigeria. This finding corroborate with Fatoki (2014) in his study, he explores the influence of micro-finance institutions towards promoting green business models in South Africa. He posted that micro-finance helps small and medium entrepreneurs to adopt sustainable business practise through the provision of financial support and capacity training.

CONCLUSION

This study investigates how micro-financing is a strategic tool for sustainable green entrepreneurship. The major focus of the study is selected micro-finance institutions as well as selected green entrepreneurs in the Lagos metropolis. This study introduced a distinctive approach by considering the strategic role played by micro-finance institutions in providing funds to green entrepreneurs, thereby promoting sustainable economic development.

Over the years, environmental challenges have been a global concern, and Nigeria as a country is not excluded from the fallout of climate change, waste management, pollution, and deforestation. The study highlighted how micro-finance institutions have encouraged green entrepreneurs through the provision of micro-loans in the area of micro-carbon reduction through solar energy projects; suitable agricultural practice through bio-technology, and sustainable waste management through waste re-cycling ventures.

This study asserts that increasing investment in green entrepreneurship is vital for economic growth and a sustainable environment. The pivotal role played by micro-finance institutions in achieving the above cannot be overemphasised. Therefore, the study concludes that socio-economic policies that promotes investments in green business ventures will positively impact economic growth and sustainable environmental development in Nigeria.

CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This study examined micro-financing as a catalyst for sustainable green entrepreneurship. It emphasized the views and opinions of various scholars in the specialized field. Theories of financial inclusion and a resources based view were adopted, and the findings revealed that not much attention has been given to the aforementioned. The study contributes the following to existing knowledge:

1. Micro-finance institutions can be game changers in achieving economic growth and a sustainable environment.
2. Issues of environmental pollution and degradation could be solved through provision of green loans and carbon credits by micro-finance institutions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

After a careful analysis of the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- * Policymakers should design more robust policies and regulations that could promote micro-finance products, specifically structures towards green entrepreneurship. Such products should accommodate flexible funding alternatives, reduced interest rates and expanded repayment terms to cater to the unique needs of environmentally sustainable business setup.
- * There should be application of technology in green entrepreneurship. This is achieved by micro-finance institutions giving priority to investments in provision of technological solution that enhance efficiency, and resilience of green business ventures. For instances, provision of finance in renewable energy installations, waste recycling technologies and eco-friendly farming practices can boost sustainable environment significantly.
- * Entrepreneurs and new businesses seeking green ventures should receive adequate training on sustainable business practices, effective usage of micro-finance institution products and financial literacy skills. These capacity building will enable them to be better managers as well as scale up their green business sustainability.
- * Policy incentives for green entrepreneurs such as tax breaks, subsidies or grants to Micro-finance institutions that support green ventures can be implemented by the government. This will greatly encourage small and medium business innovators to explore environmentally friendly ventures while also promoting financial inclusion for small scale entrepreneurs.

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